

A watercolor illustration of a rural landscape. On the left, a tall, cylindrical stone tower with a conical roof and a weather vane stands on a grassy slope. To the right, several stone buildings with gabled roofs are situated on a hillside. The scene is rendered in soft, painterly tones.

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ARDMORE CO. WATERFORD HERITAGE TRAIL

ARDMORE TIDY TOWNS 2024

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ARDMORE TIDY TOWNS

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Cover: Gabriel Beranger copy of a Charles Vallancey drawing of Ardmore ca. 1770. Copyright RIA

Ardmore Tidy Towns is a voluntary group engaging in the maintenance of Ardmore village, Co. Waterford. This guide is a heritage project for Ardmore Tidy Towns and has been written by local archaeologists Martha Hannon and John Tierney. The guide is largely based on the work of local historians such as Siobhán Lincoln (RIP). Fr Dónal O'Connor, Tommy Mooney, James Quain, Liam Suipéil and Richard Harrington.

As part of the EU Horizon SECReTour project we are experimenting with combining printed brochures, a pop-up trail with weatherproof cards at some of the points of interest and a regularly edited digital guide made available online. The first version of the trail starts with eight points of interest and we intend to add more sites as the Summer goes on.

Recent research on Ardmore's heritage has been carried out by Jacinta Kiely, Dr Paul MacCotter, Dave Pollock, John Tierney and Martha Hannon. The research was funded by various bodies primarily through the office of Bernadette Guest, Heritage Officer, Waterford Co. Council. Thanks to all who support Ardmore Tidy Towns.

Ideas, corrections, discussion? Please contact us on <https://www.facebook.com/ardmoregrangeheritagegroup>

MAP

In the following pages links can be activated using the QR codes or by clicking on the red boxes on those pages.

1. Bronze Age Burnt Mound

Situated in Dysert townland this is the oldest identified archaeological site in Ardmore and is recognisable as a 15m wide circle of dark, charcoal-rich soil with heat shattered stone. 4,000 years ago animals were butchered and cooked here by the families who farmed this land. A pit was dug into the ground and due to the high level of groundwater here, the pit filled with water. Hot stones from a nearby fire were rolled into the water to form a boiling pit for meat from the butcher animals.

There are over 240 known burnt mounds (*fulachta fiadh*) in Waterford and approx. 7000 in Ireland. A burnt mound is visible near Holy Cross cemetery and one was excavated near the sewage treatment plant in Monea.

Part of a working farm please do not enter the field.

2. Round tower graveyard

This large monastic site (approx 300m N-S x 150m) has been in continuous use as a religious site since the 5th century AD, and was home to an order of monks known as the *Ceile Dé* in the 8th & 9th centuries. The inner sanctum of the monastery survives as the old graveyard and was once the centre of what may be called the Cult of St. Declan, which stretched over much of mid and south Munster. St Declan's grave may be the original saints grave making it perhaps the oldest recognisable Christian grave in Ireland. The round tower and cathedral were built as part of political power games between Ardmore and Lismore in the mid 12th century when Bishop Eugene of Ardmore proved politically adept in his dealings with the new Anglo-Norman overlords to Ardmore's benefit. *See QR code for separate graveyard trail.*

3. Ardmore's Lost Castle

Website

The exact location of the 'lost castle' of Ardmore is uncertain.

Documentary evidence dating to the siege of 1642 suggests that it was located a pistol-shot downhill from the cathedral. The castle was subject to two sieges in the religious wars of 1642. The Catholic side captured it from the Protestant Sir John Brelsford earlier that year and were subsequently besieged and massacred in August by the Protestant forces of the sons of Richard Boyle, Earl Of Cork. Historian Richard Harrington has an interesting analysis of the siege and was the first to point out that there were two successive sieges of Ardmore castle. In all, 117 Catholic defenders of the castle were captured and hanged. Drone survey ground models are now revealing a rectangular enclosure measuring 52m x 46m just north of the Farrengarret farm building complex which may be a defensive enclosure ie. part of the 'lost castle'. See *the QR code for more.*

4. St Paul's Church (COI)

Until the 1830s Church of Ireland parishioners worshipped in the chancel of the cathedral. By then the church within the chancel was falling into disrepair, resulting in permission being granted by the Privy Council to build a new church in this location. The first service in the new church was celebrated in 1839. The octagonal-shaped baptismal font, which is said to date to the 16th century, was transferred from the cathedral to this church. The novelist Molly Keane who resided in Ardmore, died in 1996 and is buried in St. Paul's graveyard. She is best known for her novel, 'Good Behaviour' (1981) which was short-listed for the Booker Prize.

The QR code links to a community survey of the gravestones in the churchyard.

5. St. Declan's Church (RC)

This Catholic Church was built during the decade when Rev. Fr. P. McGrath was parish priest (1836-1846) in response to Catholic Emancipation & increased power conceded to the Church from Westminster. Prior to this Catholics practiced their faith in a mass house above the pier. Siobhán Lincoln tells us for many years after construction, this church was without seating followed by a period when seating was provided only around the walls of the interior. During the 1970's the high altar was replaced by the present arrangement, allowing the priest to face the congregation. The exterior bell dates to 1927 and was founded by Matthew Byrne of the Fountain Head Bell Foundry, Dublin. The two holy water fountains inside the entrance gate are believed to have been found in the pre-Emancipation mass house on Cliff Row (Quain 1987).

6. The Boat Cove

In Irish, the cove is referred to as *Gaibhlín Mór* (pronounced guy-leen, meaning a small rocky inlet). Liam Suipéil's 2019 book **The Personality of a Coastline** is a detailed record of local coastal place names and is well worth a read - the QR code links to an online version of Liam's work. Zoom in to Ardmore to see the placenames. Ardmore has a long fishing heritage including the early 1600s, when industrial fish processing was set up by the Earl of Cork, Richard Boyle. Situated nearby was Boyle's 'fish palace' a huge timber hall measuring 46m long and 6.5m wide (ie. 14m longer than St Declan's church) (Rynne 2018). Today, only a few boats fish in Ardmore bay. In the past, pilchard, sprat, salmon, mackerel, herring and lobster were caught, but by the 1980's, as fish stocks decreased, various restrictions, for instance on mesh sizes and fishing licences, were put in place.

7. Cliff Row

Cliff Row is a picturesque row of small one and two-storey houses overlooking Ardmore Bay, some retain original architectural features eg. Roserie Cottage which may have consisted of two smaller cottages originally. The row is shown as an isolated group of 10-14 structures on the 1818 & 1840 historic maps. Rent Books dating to the 1880/90s show the O'Dell landlord's agent, John Pedder Furlong, collecting rent from the occupants of these cottages. Griffiths Valuation from 1851 lists Ryan, Corbett, Foley, Mahony, Quain, Droghan, Troy and Farrell surnames as Cliff Row tenants; fishing families as evidenced by the 1901 census. There are no signs these houses were ever thatched and are probably early 1800s in origin. Prior to the construction of St. Declan's Church in the 1830s, parishioners attended mass in a chapel in this row, exact location uncertain.

Siobhán Lincoln's Book

8. Díseart Déagláin

Local lore and place name evidence tell us St.

Declan lived here in a cell as a hermit in the fifth century AD, however no upstanding remains from that period survive. What is present are a ruined medieval parish church (probably dating to the 1200s), measuring 23m x 6m, and the holy well (the superstructure for which probably dates to the late 1790s). This parish church represents the first of a series of at least three parish churches in Ardmore village ie. this medieval church, the mass house in Cliff Row and the present day St. Declan's Church. A graveyard is marked here in the 1840 OS map and also in the 1851 Griffiths Valuation. On the eve of St. Declan's feast day, 23rd July, 'rounds' or 'stations' are performed here. Two small, late medieval stone cruciforms ie. showing the crucified Christ, adorn the well (see QR code for annotated 3D model).

3D Model

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